

COMPARISON OF DESTRUCTIVE AND NON-DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION TECHNIQUES USED WITH COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

The capabilities of Non-Destructive-Evaluation (NDE) and Destructive-Evaluation (DE) techniques such as radiography, ultrasonic C-scan, emission acoustic and deply are considered with respect to the study of damage in carbon-epoxy material. The above methods have been used for the detection and assesment of damage in $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_s$ specimens. Transverse matrix cracks in the 90° plies is the first failure mode occured in these symmetrically stacked specimens. X-rays radiography and ultrasonic C-scan permitted their location and identification. Monitoring acoustic emission produced by the cracks indicated their presence. Verification was accomplished by microscopic examination and by deplying the material.

KEYWORDS : Composites; destructive/non-destructive evaluation; deply technique; X-ray radiography; ultrasonic C-scan; acoustic emission.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite have a high strength-to-weight ratio which makes them attractive for many structural applications. The response of composite materials to these applications depends on the layer's orientation, on the stacking sequences and on the nature of the applied load. It is well known that a complex damage state can develop in composite materials when they are subjected to mechanical loading. Reliable Non-Destructive-Evaluation (NDE) and Destructive-Evaluation (DE) techniques are required in order to assess

the damage and understand the mechanisms. The most common DE method to study damage is microscopic examination. The observation of polished composite specimens can reveal microcracks between lamina, matrix cracks within a lamina, delamination and fibre fracture. Although this visual inspection is easily done, it allows examination only of the plane of the specimen section. The deply technique conceived and experimental development initiated at the Lockheed-Georgia Company [1-3], provides more details of damage. This technique consists of a partial pyrolysis of the resin matrix and permits the precise observation of fibre fracture within each lamina. These two techniques permit the evaluation of damage in the composite laminate but they are tedious, time-consuming and destroy completely the material. The NDE methods were investigated to find a better solution to study damage keeping intact the material specimen. Enhanced X-ray radiography has been usually employed as a NDE technique to detect damage. Nevertheless, there appear to be contradictory findings about what types of damage can be detect by X-ray radiography [4-7]. Prakash was able to detect thermal cracks by radiography but Harris was unable to find them; Nevadunsky et al. suggests that voids, cracks and porosity can be identified but neither voids neither cracks were found by Salkind in his tests. It seems that the efficiency of this technique depends essentially on the experimental conditions. To maximize the information available from radiography and to permit best resolution to detect damage, one has to be assured of having good contrast from the X-ray radiographic technique. Among the NDE methods used, ultrasonic inspection systems have been developed for a number of years to examine the defects of composite material, both during the manufacturing process and during loading [8]. In recent years, ultrasonic C-scan systems have been widely assisted by computer, test results are presented with colour images permitting the identification of damage zones. Although informative, the radiographs and C-scan images do not give ideas about the progress of damage. Acoustic Emission (A.E) has been considered in the last few years as a great potential NDE technique for continuously monitoring the integrity of carbon-epoxy composite material. Hamstad [9-10] compared A.E obtained from filament-wound glass fibre pressure vessels and filament-wound carbon fibre pressure vessels and concluded that the differences in A.E patterns at the point of failure resulted from the fewer number of carbon fibre fractures. Fuwa et al. [11-14] have investigated A.E to identify and characterize the mechanisms fracture of composite; they brought out that there could be ambiguities in the interpretation of the A.E from composite material since the relative large fracture surface areas were associated with matrix cracking and delamination. Several other authors have reported success in the use of amplitude distributions to distinguish A.E sources and hence identify failure modes [15-19]. The use of computerized systems and signal processing techniques in the recent years has improved significantly the capability of the A.E technique.

In the present work, symmetrically stacked specimens (0° , 90°) were used. To produce specimens containing progressive amounts of damage, similar specimens of each type were loaded to failure and different load levels below ultimate strength. After loading specimens were inspected for damage using the NDE and DE techniques mentioned above. During the mechanical test of each specimen, A.E was monitored as a function of load. The data recorded were analyzed and correlated with the micrographs and with the results obtained from the X-ray radiography, the ultrasonic C-scan, the deply techniques.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP AND TEST PROCEDURE

2.1. Specimen fabrication

The composite material tested was known commercially as T300/M10 and consisted of carbon fibre T300 reinforced epoxy resin M10. The material was made by filament winding and was cured at 125°C for 2 hours followed by postcuring at 150°C for 1 hour. The specimens tested were cut from the cross-ply laminated plates 500x500 mm with a diamond-plated wheel with adequate water supply to avoid heating of the material. Aluminium endtabs were bonded onto all of the specimens to reduce grip noise. They were also used to facilitate the alignment of the specimen in the grips.

2.2. Mechanical tests to induce damage

Seven specimens were loaded in tension using a Zwick automated test machine. Four replicate specimens, selected at random, were tested to failure. Based on the results of failure tests, three load levels were selected for the remaining specimens. The tests were performed in position control at a ram movement rate of 0.5mm/min and were conducted at room temperature.

2.3. Acoustic Emission procedure

Acoustic Emission (A.E) was monitored during the mechanical tensile tests. Three type of data were collected : event counts, event duration and event amplitude. The piezo-electric transducer with a resonant frequency of 150 KHZ was positioned in the middle of the specimen using a silicon gel as an acoustic couplant at the interface. The transducer was connected to a 40 dB, 100-300 KHz bandpass preamplifier which fed the signal to a LOCAN-AT A.E analyzer. An additional 38 dB was provided by the amplifier internal to the analyzer and the threshold was set to 35 dB. The A.E analyzer was calibrated by simulating A.E with a No.2 graphite lead break before each test. In parallel with the A.E data, a load signal from the Zwick mechanical test machine was also recorded simultaneously with the A.E signal and sent to the analyzer. All the signals were stored on the hard disk and analyzed subsequently with a replay software in order to correlate A.E with load and damage.

2.4. X-ray radiography

The specimens subjected to a load level below ultimate failure were inspected using enhanced X-ray radiography. In order to bring out details of damage an X-ray penetrant was used. With a penetrant, damage appears darker in the radiographs. The best penetrant which provides a good contrast between the damage and the composite is the alcohol-zinc iodide solution (ZnI_2). It was shown that this solution is not toxic or dangerous as is the case with the tetrabromoethane (TBE) and diiodobutane (DIB) solutions. The specimens were soaked in the ZnI_2 solution for 30 minutes. After the soak interval, the specimens were removed from the solution and the excess penetrant was removed from the surface of the specimens. The specimens were then ready for radiography-tests. They were placed at a distance of 1m from the X-ray generator. They were radiographed at 25KV and 2.5mA with a beryllium window. The optimum exposure times were 2min for the $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_S$ specimens.

2.5. Ultrasonic C-scan

After the radiographic tests, the specimens were inspected by ultrasonic attenuation C-scan pulse-echo system. This technique is based on the elastic waves propagation in the material using a single transducer to send and receive the acoustic pulse from one side of the specimen after being reflected from the opposite face. The reflected echo signal from the front and back surfaces of the specimen determines an electronic gate. The specimen is immersed in water which serves both as a uniform coupling medium to transmit the sound waves between the transducer and the specimen and delay line for the ultrasonic signal. The signal levels at each point and depth is displayed as the transducer is scanned across the specimen. In the present work, the ultrasonic tests were conducted with a 10 Hz transducer and the width of electronic gate was selected so that the front surface echo was excluded. The variation of signal levels was stored in a computer and then analyzed with a SOFRATEST SFT 4001C card to provide informations about damaged zone of the specimen.

2.6 Deply inspection

Following non-destructive inspection, the specimens were used for destructive evaluation. A segment of each specimen was removed and inspected by deply technique. In order to mark matrix fractures, the sample was filled with a gold chloride diethylether solution. After approximately 30 minutes, it was removed and allowed to air dry. The solution was supposed to have sufficient time to infiltrate into matrix damage. An excess solution on the sample was removed by wiping with acetone moistened cotton and the sample was heated to 65°C in order to allow the solvent to volatilize before proceeding to the deply. The sample was then placed in a ceramic boat and the boat containing the sample was introduced into a furnace maintained at 420°C for 1 hour. The sample with the partially pyrolyzed resin matrix was then removed from the furnace and the boat. After cooling, the individual laminae were unstacked and lifted using a transparent tape. Each lamina was stucked on a card with a double coated tape to facilitate the microscopic study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three load levels were selected for $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_S$ specimens. The testing procedure was to load a specimen, remove it from the test machine, inspect it by X-ray radiography and then scan it. Following the ultrasonic scanning, the coupons were sectioned for microscopic examination and deplying. The acoustic emissions generated during the loading of each specimen have been monitored in order to detect damage occurring within the specimen. The radiographic test results of the specimens are presented in Figure 1. This figure shows the capability of the radiography technique for assessing the damage due to loading. Dark areas in these radiographs indicate damaged zones where a penetrant has permeated into the voids.

Specimen A-1 was loaded to 4.5 kN which represented 25% of the ultimate load P^* . Radiography revealed no matrix cracks but it is possible that there were cracks which were too small to be detected. Radiograph of the specimen A-2 which was loaded to 50% P^* , indicated small cracks in the matrix in planes perpendicular to the load. These transverse matrix cracks increased with increases in load and were more pronounced as shown on the radiograph of the specimen A-3, loaded to 75% P^* . These damage indications were present on the ultrasonic C-scan images as represented in the Figure 2. The lack of material observed at the extremity of the

specimen A-3 was due to warpage of the specimen. The radiographic and ultrasonic C-scan techniques produced similarly damaged zones for each specimen. Nevertheless, ultrasonic C-scan gave only indications about the damaged zones but was not able to inform us about the nature of the damage. Acoustic emission (A.E) results are presented in Figure 3. The A.E amplitude distribution histogram shows that events were recorded throughout the range 40-100 dB, but it can be observed that the peaks were build up between 40-60 dB. Their position was unchanging from a level load to another but it rose sharply near the 40 dB. It is generally accepted that the events with low, middle and high range amplitude are generated by matrix cracking, debonding at fibre-matrix interface and fibre fracture respectively. Therefore, it is considered that the damage of the (0°,90°) is dominated by matrix cracking. As a consequence the specimens were sectioned on the damaged zones for microscopic examination. Transverse matrix cracks were confirmed. As shown in the radiograph of the specimen A-2 and the micrographs in Figure 4, the cracks began at first on the edge of the specimen, near the 0°/90° interface. They went completely across the thickness of the specimen when the load increased.

It is of interest to point out that the significant A.E events were recorded throughout the range 60-80 dB for the ultimate load specimen. The photograph of the failure specimen A-4 produced by the radiography (Figure 1) suggests that other damage mechanism such as fibre fracture occurred before the specimen were completely broken. Fibre failure started at a higher load than matrix cracks and occurred at the end of the test. No delamination was seen on the specimen or on the X-ray radiograph.

Using the deply technique, it was found that the matrix cracks indications were also observed on the surface of the depliy laminae. These indications were marked by a gold solution and were found on the 90° plies (Figure 5). No fibre fracture was found on any of the lamina of the A-1 and A-2 specimens. It appeared in the 0° direction of the specimen A-3 which was loaded to 75% P* (Figure 6). In this work, no attempt was made to correlate quantitatively the A.E data with damage identified by the deply analysis, because only a partial of the specimens were examined by deplying. Nevertheless, through our results, agreement was found between these techniques.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study provided a test for measuring the capability of the NDE and DE techniques. The NDE techniques are excellent for detecting damage in composite material. Radiography and ultrasonic C-scan results showed rather close agreement. They proved to be a good indicator of damage but the ultrasonic C-scan is not a useful tool to identify it. The radiography method shows great promise. It has been established that enhanced X-ray radiography using the zinc iodide solution as an opaque penetrant can assess damage zone growth. The method is specially efficient for studying transverse matrix cracks. Nevertheless both methods mentioned above can not predict damage. Acoustic emission appears to offer a great potential to study damage during the mechanical test. However, the analyze of A.E data from composite is still open for discussion. The destructive evaluation procedures presented in this work can also reveal damage in composite material. The deply technique and the microscopic examination can provide complementary informations of damage such as fibre fracture or cracks which are too small to be detect by other methods. These destructive techniques do not

require an advanced equipment. However they are time-consuming and destroy completely the material. The challenge is to develop non-destructive technique that can detect damages, locate them and define their characteristic nature.

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Figure 1. Radiographic test results.

specimen A-1

specimen A-2

specimen A-3

attenuation

Figure 2. Ultrasonic C-scan pictures.

Figure 3. Amplitude histograms obtained at different load levels for T300/M10 specimens.

50 μm

Figure 4. Micrographs showing matrix cracks in the $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_5$ laminate. The 90° fibres are circular.

Figure 5. View of matrix cracks marked with a gold chloride solution.

Figure 6. Fibre fracture on the lamina of the specimen A-3.

